

Melliferous Trees, Shrubs and Grasses in Mediterranean Areas

www.af4eu.eu

The Docufilm "More Than Honey" poster

Docufilm "More Than Honey" by Markus Imhoof (2012): a cry of alarm for the state of bees in much of the world. Diseases and pests, environmental instability and climate change, indiscriminate use of pesticides and loss of biodiversity, these are the most serious contributing causes that are leading to the erosion of the world's beekeeping heritage. Understanding the invaluable contribution of bees and pollinating insects to support biodiversity and functionality in ecosystems is an essential objective of any activity that intends to enhance and protect the territory and agriculture. It is necessary to support environmental protection and the protection of biodiversity as prerequisites for sustainable land use. The protection activities, starting from the analysis of local realities, are contextualized in a school of thought that considers environmental complexity as a unifying value on a global scale. Agriculture, in particular, must be brought back towards environmental structures and cultivation practices that are more respectful of the biodiversity content of the places. The recovery of ancient agroforestry practices and their reinterpretation in a scientific perspective are elements that research and political decision-makers are currently looking at with attention. Beekeeping must be placed in this network of thoughts and actions, becoming the object of research and applications aimed at the recovery and revival of agroecosystems. The case of the reconstitution of agroecosystems suitable for pollinating insects must be based on the planting of arboreal-shrubby species adapted to the local pedoclimatic conditions. At the same time, the farm crop plans must adopt rotations and cover crops favourable to melliferous production. This is particularly desirable in the Mediterranean environment where complex biodiversity frames the intrinsic fragility of the ecosystem.

Marco Lauteri, Francesca Chiocchini,
Marco Ciolfi, Cinzia Pellegrini, Enrico
Petrangeli, Pierluigi Paris

CNR-IRET Team

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.